

The advantages of foreign investments involved in the education system in the development of the national economy of the country

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Abstract. *This article talks about the normative and legal bases for attracting foreign investments and current indicators, the importance of foreign investments in the development of the country's national economy and their effectiveness.*

Key words. *Foreign investment, national economy, education system, economic development, educational quality, innovation, entrepreneurship, financial institutions.*

Introduction

In the context of Uzbekistan, the infusion of foreign investments into the education system stands as a pivotal driver for the nation's economic development. The advantages of leveraging foreign investments in education reverberate across the fabric of the national economy, offering a pathway towards sustainable growth, enhanced competitiveness, and human capital development.

As Uzbekistan continues its journey towards economic diversification and modernization, foreign investments in the education sector present a myriad of opportunities and advantages. These advantages include the enhancement of educational infrastructure and resources, the elevation of academic standards, the promotion of innovation and entrepreneurship, alignment with industry demands, increased opportunities for educational access, and the reinforcement of lifelong learning initiatives.

Through strategic partnerships and targeted foreign investments in education, Uzbekistan can harness the transformative power of these resources to nurture a skilled workforce, foster technological advancements, and propel the country towards economic prosperity. By embracing foreign investments in education, Uzbekistan can pave the way for a knowledge-based economy, where education serves as a catalyst for social progress and sustainable development.

The head of our country mentioned the following at the second Tashkent international investment forum: As a result of the reforms, it was noted that the status of Uzbekistan as a country with the highest diversified economy in the region has been further strengthened. In one year, about 100,000 new enterprises were established, the annual volume of foreign investments reached 10 billion dollars or increased 3 times compared to 2017, when the reforms began, about 1 million people were lifted out of poverty, and the poverty rate decreased from 17% to 14% dropped [1]. At the time of the beginning of the reforms, this indicator was higher than 30 percent. The head of our state expressed deep gratitude and high respect to all foreign and domestic investors, governments of partner countries, and international financial institutions, who contribute to such achievements.

Acceleration of globalization processes in the world requires increasing the possibility of attracting foreign investments in the economy of countries. In this regard, a number of measures are being implemented in our country. In particular, in the investment policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025, increasing the competitiveness and balance of the economy, developing the production and export potential, developing the regions and increasing the welfare of the population, the volume of centralized investments until the end of 2025 is 37.5% of GDP, that is, The main goal of the investment policy is to reach 1002.5 billion sums [2].

The development of international trade between countries, the expansion and improvement of production integration is the reason for further liberalization of foreign economic activity.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158, the strategy “Uzbekistan – 2030” was developed. According to it, further

increasing the investment attractiveness of our country, assimilation of 250 billion dollars of investments in our country, including 110 billion dollars of foreign investments and 30 billion dollars of public-private partnerships, maintaining the investment rating of the regions, based on the capabilities of each region, the main goals of further increasing its attractiveness for investors were set [3].

Methodology

Analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, abstract-logical, expert methods were used during the research of the article. Also, the advantages of foreign investments attracted to the education system of investments in human capital in the development of the national economy of Uzbekistan scientific conclusions and proposals were developed.

Analysis and results

World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that investment is the “driver of the economy”. With the investment, new technologies, advanced experiences, and highly qualified specialists will enter various fields and sectors, regions, and entrepreneurship will develop rapidly.

The importance of foreign investments in the development of the national economy is explained by the following:

- firstly, it introduces modern techniques and technologies into production and develops the production of products intended for export;

- secondly, it makes it possible to start the production of goods that replace imports and for this purpose to direct foreign investments to the priority sectors of the economy and ultimately to ensure the standard of living of the population;

- thirdly, it provides jobs for the growing population by developing small business, private entrepreneurship and accelerating agricultural production;

- fourthly, it renews and technically re-equips the outdated production capacities, material and technical base of enterprises;

- fifthly, they will help to establish natural resource processing enterprises, tax revenue will increase in the state budget.

Foreign investments in the education system can bring about numerous advantages that have the potential to significantly impact the development of a country's national economy. Below is an analysis of some key advantages of foreign investments in the education sector and how they contribute to economic growth:

1. **Enhanced Infrastructure and Resources:** Foreign investments can help improve the physical infrastructure of educational institutions by providing funding for modern facilities, equipment, and technology. This can create a more conducive learning environment and attract both students and skilled educators, ultimately boosting the quality of education.

2. **Elevated Educational Quality:** Foreign investments often come with expertise and best practices from global educational standards. This can lead to the implementation of innovative teaching methods, curriculum enhancements, and quality assurance mechanisms, raising the overall standard of education in the country.

3. **Promotion of Innovation and Entrepreneurship:** Foreign investments can stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship within the education sector by supporting research and development initiatives, incubating startups, and fostering a culture of creativity among students and educators. This can lead to the generation of new ideas, products, and services that drive economic growth.

4. **Alignment with Industry Needs:** Foreign investments can help align educational programs with the requirements of industries, ensuring that graduates are equipped with relevant skills and knowledge that match the demands of the job market. This alignment can reduce unemployment rates, bridge skills gaps, and improve productivity in key sectors of the economy.

5. **Increased Access to Education:** By investing in educational infrastructure and scholarship programs, foreign investments can expand access to education for marginalized communities and underserved regions. This can lead to a more educated and skilled workforce, empowering individuals to contribute to the economy.

6. **Support for Lifelong Learning:** Foreign investments can support lifelong learning initiatives, such as continuing education programs and skill development

courses, which are essential for maintaining a dynamic and adaptable workforce in an ever-evolving economy.

7. Technological Advancements: Foreign investments in education often involve the integration of advanced technologies and digital tools in teaching and learning processes. This can enhance educational outcomes, promote digital literacy, and prepare individuals for roles in the digital economy.

There are a number of regulatory legal documents for investment projects in the education system. In particular, they include:

- Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to implement the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2023 – 2025” (28.12.2022);

- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and introduction of new approaches and mechanisms of investment project management" (30.12.2021) decision;

- Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On ensuring the effectiveness of investment projects implemented at the expense of the state debt” (06.10.2020);

- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030” (29.10.2020);

- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" (12.25.2019);

- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the mechanisms of attracting foreign aid funds and work with donors" (10.10.2019);

- Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to introduce new management principles into the system of higher and secondary special education" (11.07.2019).

Funds from international financial institutions are used to finance the education system. Also, under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, the project of strengthening the material and technical base of higher education institutions

with the participation of the Islamic Development Bank will provide higher education institutions with 32.5 million equipment with modern teaching laboratory equipment is envisaged.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 286 of May 16, 2024 “On measures to implement the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the II quarter of 2024”, Higher education in the II quarter of 2024, 0.2 million within the framework of the project of strengthening the material and technical base of higher education institutions with the participation of the Islamic Development Bank under the Ministry of Science and Innovation. USD appropriation is set.

In 2023, within the framework of this project, 60 higher education institutions will receive 16.7 million dollars educational laboratories were equipped with equipment. According to the 2023 Investment Program, 9.1 million USD funds (100 percent) were used [4].

Currently, works within the framework of the project are being carried out according to the established schedule. Within the framework of the project implemented in 2024, 60 higher education institutions will be financed by 15.8 million dollars. It is planned to equip with laboratory equipment.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 286 dated May 16, 2024 "On measures to implement the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the II quarter of 2024" in the II quarter of 2024, higher education institutions In order to strengthen the material and technical base, the total cost with the participation of international donor organizations is 5.6 million dollars. It is planned to implement US dollar direct investment projects.

3.1 million US dollar investment funds were used. 5.6 million (100% compared to the plan) set by the end of the II quarter. US dollar funds have been embezzled.

There are a number of projects planned to be implemented in the future for the development of higher education including the participation of the German KfW Bank in 2024-2027 with a total cost of 42.0 million. It is planned to implement the project “Professional Education System Improvement” equal to one euro.

Development and approval of project documents is scheduled by the Ministry in 2024. It is planned to improve the professional education system within this project.

Also, in 2024-2028, with the participation of Exim Bank of Korea, the total cost is 50.0 million dollars. It is planned to implement the project “Strengthening the material and technical base of professional educational institutions” worth USD [5].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the advantages of foreign investments in Uzbekistan’s education system present a transformative opportunity to propel the nation towards economic prosperity and sustainable development. By leveraging foreign capital strategically within the education sector, Uzbekistan can enhance its educational infrastructure, elevate academic standards, foster innovation and entrepreneurship, align educational programs with industry needs, expand access to education, and support lifelong learning initiatives.

These advantages collectively contribute to the development of a skilled workforce, equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving global economy. Furthermore, foreign investments in education can catalyze technological advancements, drive productivity, and enhance the country’s competitiveness on the international stage.

As Uzbekistan continues its journey towards economic diversification and modernization, foreign investments in education stand as a key driver for building a knowledge-based economy and shaping a brighter future for generations to come. By embracing these advantages and fostering a culture of educational excellence, Uzbekistan can position itself as a hub of innovation, talent, and economic growth in the region.

Literature review

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